

The Need to Formulate a Competency Working with Information in the Educational System

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Abstract:

Today, the development of the digital economy is significant in the management of the state and society, as well as in the integration of world countries. In this context, in the development of the digital economy, it is important to formulate a working competency with information. In this article, the content and essence of the compensation for working with the information necessary for the development of the digital economy is widely disclosed. It also provides the necessary recommendations for its formation and development.

Keywords: knowledge, enlightenment, digital economy, information, electronic calculation, competence, intelligence, culture of working with information, ergonomics,

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INTRODUCTION

The fact that the flow of information and the level of its use are increasing represents the scientific landscape of the modern world. The increase in the scale of information is reducing the opportunities for its management and security. In particular, it requires great potential to be able to use it in sorting out, processing and developing new knowledge from within.

The scientific landscape of the world is one of the highest levels of systematized knowledge. It expresses a stable fundamental principle and the sum of its sections, creates a system of knowledge corresponding to the level of development of science, at the same time serves as a theoretical basis for the end of scientific knowledge development and new knowledge. However, in today's informed society, not only production, but also the whole system of lifestyle and values change. In such a society, intelligence, knowledge is assimilated and introduced into consumption, as a result of which the individual is regularly engaged in mental labor [1].

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Since the XXI century is the age of information and intelligence, in such an informed society people are required to have fully mastered the culture of working with information and the skills to engage in intelligent labor. Working with information in a purposeful manner, with the aim of mastering them, requires processing, computerized information technology, the application of modern technical tools and methods – the culture of working with information. Only people with a high level of Information Culture will be able to accurately take natural, socio-economic, environmental and pedagogical resources into account.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

I. In the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "The action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" in February 7, 2017, priority tasks for the further acceleration of the development of our country for 2017-2021 were defined. The work aimed at developing the social sphere has identified important tasks for radically improving the quality of Education.

In an appeal sent to the Supreme Assembly by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev in January 24, 2020 was declared as "the year of development of Science, Education and digital economy", and a special attention was paid to the development of science and technology. In particular, as the eastern wise men say:

The greatest wealth is intelligence and science,
The greatest legacy is a good upbringing,
The greatest poverty is ignorance!

Therefore, it is necessary to master modern knowledge, to be truly enlightened and the owner of a high culture, to become a continuous vital need.

In this appeal, it was noted that the improvement of the results of our reforms should not only be used by the state bodies, but also the society itself should be the initiator of

reforms and people should be more active by studying all the modern knowledge, achieving perfection and increasing productivity [2].

In the reforms carried out in all parts of education in the training of the new generation of personnel, the criteria for being an initiative reformer, strategic thinker, educated and skilled person are the priorities. First of all, knowledge and high spirituality are needed in order to increase the level of knowledge of the members of our society as a whole. Apparently, in this process, attention is paid to the transformation of human resources into human capital.

On April 6, 2017, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the "State educational standards of general secondary and secondary special vocational education". This state standard of education is based on the competency criterion, which provides the formation of special competences on the base and science in education recipients.

Competence is a social requirement put in advance on the educational preparation by the educator for effective activity in a particular field [3].

Competency is a set of personal qualities (knowledge, skills, abilities) of the educator, determined by the experience gained in his activities in the established social and personal sphere [3].

Competency is necessary for a person to have a minimum of experience that he / she must have when applying the competences. According to it, the following 6 types of base concomitant should be formed:

- communicative competence;
- competency in working with information;
- self-development competence as an individual;
- Socially active civil competence;
- General information, mathematical literacy;

To be aware of Science and technology innovations and to use competency.

Taking this into account, we can say that the most important thing in the six compartments are the information processing compartments. Others are formed precisely on the basis of this, that is, depending on the level and validity of the information received, it is possible to determine the quality of self-development as a person, socially active citizenship, the formation of universal compensations. The reason, let us say, is that in a student or educator who has mastered negative information, there will never be a formation of positive social activity or exemplary moral communicative activity.

Individuals with competency in working with information will have such skills as competence working with textbooks and other sources of information, understanding the content of social systems and delineating them into fields, categorizing the sources, having a media culture, ability to analyze the indicators of the development of society, monitoring the development of the country in the spiritual and educational sphere, the skills to distinguish science information from educators, and ability to control, analyze and qualify the flow of information.

II. One of the founders of the theory of management, Anri Fayol, identified the five functions of Management in the early twentieth century as "planning", "organization", "issuing orders", "coordination" and "control", and calls Management a powerful weapon that sees the future, organizes disaster, manages the organization, coordinates the types of activities, and controls decisions and orders [4].

Through the wide introduction of digital technologies in the field of State and Public Administration, Sociology, and Economics, it is possible to achieve the following:

- improvement in the quality of products and services;
- reduction in excessive costs;
- loss of corruption;
- increase in the efficiency;
- improvement in quality of people's lives.

Digital economy means a modern economic system that forms new knowledge and digital technologies in society, business, the state within the framework of new digital concepts and opportunities such as the exchange of information on the relationship of the population with state bodies in electronic form, the provision of electronic accounts of legal entities and individuals remotely to the state tax service bodies. The introduction of an information system in notary offices is the first step towards the formation of a digital economy.

Today, together with the systematic introduction of digital technologies in all leading personnel, civil servants, in public service systems, the formation of concepts and skills in civil servants remains an urgent task.

The competency of working with information is interpreted as follows:

The ability to use available information sources (Internet, television, radio (audio-video recording), telephone, computer, email, etc.);

The ability to search, sort, process, transmit, store, secure and use the important information from the media sources and to comply with media culture;

To be able to create a database, choose the main ones and analyze them;

Be able to work with documents that are used in a daily life (be able to write simple greeting cards, fill out questionnaires, record information about himself in the hotel list, etc.);

Besides, the information flow on the web can be used even more widely. The Internet network today is represented several ways:

Information and source of knowledge;

Interactive tool of information;

All aspects of people's life – education, culture, politics-economics, social, sports, tourism and many other spheres [5].

The information and communication technologies and the world of the Internet seem to be very complicated for people. But as we get into it, our opportunities for further development of our knowledge, opening up new facets, learning foreign languages are becoming more and more important.

RECOMMENDATIONS

As a result of the excessive use of information and communication technologies, the following ergonomic ("ergonomics" Greek means ergon-work, labor and nomos –rule or rule about the labor process) problems arise:

- If educators work with computers excessively, and are less active, it affects their health to some extent;
- Users of the internet prefer virtual or online communication rather than live one. This, in turn, causes social networks (Odnoklassniki, Facebook, Twitter and etc.) to develop;
- A relatively large percentage of functional changes in the body impact on eyesight (inability to see far, astigmatism, fear of light), spine, syllable, cardiovascular and psycho-nervous systems [6].

In fact, if we look at our history, we can see that society relying on science and education became great. As today's people are well informed, society cannot achieve sustainable economic development without the development of the digital economy and the introduction of strategic elements into our lives in the world integration of all spheres, as well as strategic co-operation in our development.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in order to form a working competency with information, the following can be recommended:

- correct orientation of learners on the target strategy;
- to teach the skills to work with information in practice;
- introduction with the ways of comprehensively developing the level of competence;
- development of communication skills.
- to write an essay on the subject "Can I work with information?", or to conduct surveys, and monitor them.

Finally, it can be said that the competency to work with information plays an important role in today's digital world. Every education system should consider the inclusion of special courses that teach youngsters the necessary skills to work and use information. Today's youth should be competent to operate with data for them to survive and prosper in a competitive world where everything can be found online.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Pedagogy: encyclopedia "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan", published by State Scientific Publishing House in 2015 – p. 92. [*Pedagogika: ensiklopediya/ tuzuvchilar: Jamoa. – T.: "O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi" Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2015. – 92 b.*]

Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis /

<http://uza.uz/oz/politics/zbekiston-respublikasi-prezidenti-shavkat-mirziyevning-oliy-25-01-2020>. [*O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi / http://uza.uz/oz/politics/zbekiston-respublikasi-prezidenti-shavkat-mirziyevning-oliy-25-01-2020*]

Turdiev N.Sh. and others. Educational technologies that are aimed at the formation of students' competency in the general secondary education system. - T.: Tafakkur, 2015.

– p. 95. [Turdiev N.SH. va boshq. Umumiy oʻrta taʼlim tizimida oʻquvchilarning kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishga yoʻnaltirilgan taʼlim texnologiyalari. – T.: Tafakkur, 2015. – 95 b.]

Musurmanov R. and others. Implementation of pedagogical experience-testing activities in the system of Continuing Education (Scientific and methodical manual). [Musurmanov R. va boshqalar. Uzlusiz taʼlim tizimida pedagogik tajriba-sinov ishlarini tashkil etish mexanizmlarini joriy etish (ilmiy-metodik qoʻllanma)].

Kudratkhojaev Sh. The history of internet: formation, technical security. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2011. – p. 5. [Qudratxoʻjaev Sh. Internet tarixi: tuzilishi, texnik xavfsizlik. – T.: Oʻzbekiston, 2011. – 5 b.].

See: Soy M.N.Y., Kim Djon Xo. To ensure that the computer is ergonomically safe in school. – T.: UzPFITI, 2013. – p. 7. [Qarang: Soy M.N., Kim Djon Xo. Maktabda kompyuterning ergonomik xavsizligini taʼminlash. – T.: Oʻz PFITI, 2013. – 7 b.].

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